

Paper 4

Analysis on the correlation between self-esteem and impact of bullying behaviour among the secondary school students

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: *The Cross-sectional research study conducted among the secondary school students of private international school at Bangalore highlights the important aspects of the relationship between self-esteem and impact of bullying behavior among these secondary school students on their mental well-being, social life and academic performance. The students especially children and adolescents who are bullied but have not shared the issues with others, are usually prone to have mental health problems, if the issues are not handled at the early stage.*

Design/Methodology/Approach: *This study was aimed to identify as to whether there is any difference in self-esteem between boys and girls after being bullied. The research tools used were self-esteem questionnaire (Rosenberg, 1965), Adolescent peer Relations Instrument (BT 2010) and bullying questionnaire by (Roberto H Parada, Herbert W Marsh & Rhonda Craven (2010)). Pearson's Product moment correlation was employed to assess the relationship between self-esteem and bullying behavior. The significance of gender difference in bullying was assessed using independent sample t-test.*

Findings: *The results of the study showed that there was negligible correlation between self-esteem and bullying behavior among the students irrespective of their gender. Among the sub-categories of bullying scale, it was noted that verbal victim and self-esteem were having very low correlation (e.g., 0.118) with self-esteem. Also, the total victim and self-esteem had a very low correlation (e.g., 0.115) with self-esteem, indicating that total victims had very low positive correlation with self-esteem. The experimental study also revealed the intensity of bullying in a decreasing order "Verbal Bullying" > "Physical Bullying" > "Social Bullying". The sample in consideration showed remarkable difference in bullying behavior between boys and girls, even though the self-esteem scores were nearly similar.*

Originality/Value: *Relationship between self-esteem and bullying behaviors*

Paper Type: *Conceptual Research*

Key words: Bullying, self-esteem, victim, school adolescents, gender

1. INTRODUCTION:

Bullying in school-aged children is a worldwide occurrence of phenomenon a specific form of repeated aggressive behavior, which is intentional to hurt another individual physically, mentally and emotionally; even though, the concept of bullying at school is not new and continues to get attention from researchers, educators, parents and students. (Cornell and Mayer 2010)

Conventionally, bullying among the school students (adolescents) has been found to be a relatively consistent link between victimization, lowered self-esteem and negative emotions. Commonly, bullying in a classroom can lead to lower global self-esteem; while, self-esteem is the significant measure of personal worth, mental wellbeing, good adjustment and positive life regulating skills. However, it would be interesting to assess as to how bullying behaviors (physical, social or verbal) has an impact on the self-esteem. Additionally, the effect of bullying may

have both short and long-term effect, resulting in both physiological and psychological symptoms. (Hoover, et al 1992; Banks, 1997; Julie and John, 2003; Julie, 2007; Christine, Greg and Louise, 2013). Long-term impact of victims includes, later in life adjustments and difficulties with role confusion in adult relationships (Casey-Cannon, Hayward and Gowen 2001)

Types of bullying: Different types of bullying like physical, social and verbal to examine relationship between self-esteem that affects student behavior differently among the students' groups in diverse ways. Earlier, reports suggest that a significant relationship exists between specific types of bullying and self-esteem (Rumaya and Mansor, 2010; Sevd, 2011; Christine, Greg and Louise, 2013). Loannis (2016) opined that bullying perpetration and peer victimization leads to long-term social and clinical problem.

The present study was designed to assess the relationship between types of bullying behavior and its impact on self-esteem of victim and the level of victims' endurance. Hence, the objectives of the study were to estimate the prevalence of bullying perpetrations / victimization in Indian high school adolescents and to assess the prevalence pattern of various sub-types of bullying perpetration/victimization across different age. The outcome of the study may have relevance to the gender groups and helps physicians, counselors and pediatricians to provide guidance to adolescents and parents.

2. TEST HYPOTHESIS

- **Ho Null hypothesis:** No relationship between self-esteem and bullying
- **H1 Alternate hypothesis:** Relationship exists between self-esteem and bullying behaviors
- **Ho Null hypothesis** No relationship between different types of bullying physical, social and verbal among secondary school students.
- **H1** relationship between different types of bullying physical, social and verbal among secondary school students
- **Ho Null hypothesis:** No gender differences in self-esteem and bullying behaviors.
- **H1 Alternate hypothesis:** Gender differences in self-esteem and bullying behavior.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Research design: Non-experimental, correlational research design to find out the relationship between self-esteem and bullying behavior among secondary school student, based on specific *questionnaire*.

4. TOOLS OF ANALYSIS:

- (i) Bio graphical questionnaire to obtain essential demographic information about the participants. Like Name, age, gender, grades, socio economic status, rural or urban etc.,
- (ii) Questionnaire on self-esteem scale: RSES (Rosenberg self-esteem scale (unidimensional), 1965) It is 10 items measuring the feelings about self. Scale is, all items answered using a 4-point Likert scale, ranging from strongly agrees to strongly disagree.
- (iii) Questionnaire on bullying (APRI-BT 2010) – is a six scale adolescent peers relations Instrument: Bully /Target. Measures 3 types of behaviors used in bully (physical, verbal and social) totally 18 items used to measure. All these items were measured on a 6-point Likert responses (1 never, 2 sometimes, 3 once or twice a month 4 once a week, 5 several times a week 6 every day)
- (iv) Participants and sampling: For this study, the participants were 120 students randomly selected in the age group of 14-15, consisting of 60 boys and 60 girls. (Normal school from Bangalore).
- (v) Data analysis: Based on descriptive statistics participant's age, gender, frequency distribution, means, standard error, standard deviations and Pearson correlations coefficients calculated Statistical significance was tested by *t*-test. (SPSS software version 16 for windows OS).

5. RESULTS & DISCUSSION:

Present study was aimed to assess the levels of self-esteem and bullying among the secondary school students and to find out the relationship between self-esteem and bullying. Primarily the responses collected through questionnaire from the sample population, as a descriptive statistics analysis. Table 1 shows the mean and standard deviation of bullying status on 3 domains Verbal, social and physical of the bullying based on questionnaire along with the calculated mean of 10.68 and standard deviation of 4.211. It uses the scale of 0-30 where less than 15 indicate a problematic low self-esteem, The sample score of self-esteem mean score was 10.68 which indicate that the self-esteem of the sample was quite lower than average and the standard deviation is 4.211 indicating that there was a high variability in the scores of the sample population.

Any student who scores less than 36 (or 18 in each scale) has never been bullied or has never bullied others. There is no cut off scores for this instrument. Each student receives both a total Victim and Bully score as well as six scores for each of the scales. A score = or less than 6 on any scale means never been bullied or has never bullied others in that particular way. Fig. 1: shows the distribution of the bullying and victims scores in different bullying categories

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Mean		Std. Deviation
	Statistic	Statistic	d. Error	Statistic
Self esteem	120	10.68	.384	4.211
Verbal Bullying	120	12.60	.439	4.806
Social Bullying	120	9.85	.392	4.289
Physical Bullying	120	10.29	.372	4.074
Bullying Total	120	32.58	1.016	11.133
Verbal Victim	120	14.24	.582	6.375
Social victim	120	11.81	.570	6.239
Physical victim	120	10.13	.441	4.829
Victim Total	120	35.94	1.337	14.641
Age	120	13.87	.083	.907
Valid N (list wise)	120			

Fig. 1: Distribution of the bullying and victims scores in different bullying categories

Concerning the first domain regarding verbal bullying, mean and standard deviation are found to be 12.60 and 4.806 respectively. Hence, present sample has been verbally bullied. Regarding the second domain regarding Social bullying, the mean and standard deviation are found to be 9.85 and 4.289 respectively indicates that the present sample shows has been social bullied. The third domain regarding Physical, the mean and standard deviation are

found to be 10.29 and 4.074 respectively. Interpretation is that the present sample shows has been physical bullied.; While, the comparison between the three domains regarding verbal bullying, social bullying and physical bullying mean and standard deviation are found to be 12.60 and 4.806, 9.85 and 4.289, 10.29 and 4.074 respectively. Hence, sample group shows that the three domains, the verbal bullying was found to be having highest bullying affect than the physical bullying and the lowest affect was found in social type of bullying. Furthermore, regarding the total bullying, the mean and standard deviation were found to be 32.58 and 11.133 respectively, indicating that; the present sample has more than norms of 18 and less 36. In this domain the victim of bullying, verbal bullying, the mean and standard deviation were found to be 14.24 and 6.375 respectively, indicating some concerns for verbal bullying of victim.

Relating to the domain regarding the social victim, the mean and standard deviation were found to be 11.81 and 6.239 respectively, suggesting that social bullying of victim was higher. Concerning the domain regarding physical victim, the mean and standard deviation were found to be 10.13 and 4.829 respectively, showing that the physical bullying was found to be of lesser value.

In the domain regarding the total bullying victim mean and standard deviation were found to be 35.946 and 14.641 respectively; the interpretation, being that; the total victim bullying was found to be more than the total bullying. The domain regarding age of the participants mean and standard deviation were observed to be 13.87 and 0.907 respectively. Comparison between three domains- Verbal bullying, social bullying and physical bullying, the verbal bullying was found to have highest bullying affect than physical bullying and lowest was found in social type of bullying. A simple correlation analysis was carried out among the secondary school students. to measure the strength of relationship between self-esteem and bullying behaviours. Table 2.gives correlation matrix for self-esteem, bullying and victim

Negligible correlation was found between self-esteem and bullying behaviour among students. Among the subcategories of bullying scale, it is noted that verbal victim and self-esteem is having very low correlation (.118) with self-esteem. Hence, it can be concluded that verbal victim is having very low positive correlation with self-esteem. Also, total victim and self-esteem is having very low correlation (.115) with self-esteem, indicating that total victim is having very low positive correlation with self-esteem(Fig 2).The correlation plot indicates the relationship between all the variables in consideration, however, for the study we have to devise a relationship between Self-esteem and bullying behaviour, which is almost negligible. Hence, it can be concluded that the sample data does not provide enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

Table 2:Correlation Matrix for Self-esteem, Bullying and Victim

Correlations										
		Self esteem	Verbal Bullying	Social Bullying	Physical Bullying	Bullying Total	Verbal Victim	Social victim	Physical Victim	Victim Total
Self esteem	Pearson Correlation	1	-.040	.063	.081	.016	.118	.051	.086	.115
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.662	.495	.377	.864	.200	.577	.349	.212
	N	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120
Verbal Bullying	Pearson Correlation	-.040	1	.494**	.645**	.841**	.179	.220*	.274**	.263**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.662		.000	.000	.000	.050	.016	.002	.004
	N	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120
Social Bullying	Pearson Correlation	.063	.494**	1	.669**	.818**	.187*	.186*	.383**	.289**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.495	.000		.000	.000	.041	.042	.000	.001
	N	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120
Physical Bullying	Pearson Correlation	.081	.645**	.669**	1	.895**	.154	.249**	.377**	.293**

	Sig. (2-tailed)	.377	.000	.000		.000	.094	.006	.000	.001
	N	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120
Verbal Victim	Pearson Correlation	.118	.179	.187*	.154	.212*	1	.738**	.535**	.911**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.200	.050	.041	.094	.020		.000	.000	.000
	N	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120
Social victim	Pearson Correlation	.051	.220*	.186*	.249**	.260**	.738**	1	.419**	.860**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.577	.016	.042	.006	.004	.000		.000	.000
	N	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120
Physical Victim	Pearson Correlation	.086	.274**	.383**	.377**	.401**	.535**	.419**	1	.741**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.349	.002	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).										
*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).										

Figure 2: Correlation between Self-esteem, Bullying and Victim Scores

Table 3, depicts the gender difference in self-esteem and bullying behaviour among secondary school students. The difference in self-esteem of girls *vis-a-vis* boys is indicated in (Fig.3). The average of Self-esteem score is almost equal (10.68) in both genders while the deviation is different. Girls’ self-esteem scores range from 1 to 22, indicating that some girls are having extremely low self-esteem. The self-esteem scores for boys vary from 3 to 18, and the median is 10 which is equal to girls’ median self-esteem score.

Self-esteem scores were almost equal 10.68 in both genders, while deviation was different and there was difference between the bullying and victim Scores. As estimated in Objective 3, the sample size does not provide

enough evidence to prove any association between Self-esteem and Bullying behaviour. So there may be equivalent self-esteem score among boys and girls but the difference in bullying behaviour is quite evident in the data (Fig. 4)

The bullying was observed to be less in girls than boys per the sample. In all three categories of bullying the median score for verbal bullying in girls was 10, which is lesser than boys' score (14). Similarly, for girls, social bullying average score (7) and Physical bullying average score (7) is lesser than that of boys, whose scores are 9 and 11 for social and physical bullying, respectively. The victim scores are also lesser in girls than boys, except for being victim of social bullying where the average score for boys and girls is same (10).

Based on above observations and analysis, the null hypothesis can be rejected as there is a significant difference in self-esteem as well as bullying behaviour of girls and boys.

6. OUTCOME OF THE STUDY CONCLUSION

The present investigation indicates that there is a negligible correlation found between the self-esteem and bullying behavior of the secondary school students. When qualitatively examined, it suggests that based on the views of structured interviews with teachers, only the boys were engaged in bullying behavior rather than girls. Study results were indicative of gender differences in bullying behaviors with boys expressing more explicitly involving than girls. On comparison between three domains the verbal bullying was found to be having higher bullying affect than physical and social. Students who experienced bullying, both as a victim and offender, had significantly lower self-esteem than those who had little or no experience with bullying. Based on this study it can conclude that more data is required to establish relationship between self-esteem and bullying behavior. Maximum bullying was done verbally and has very high scores in both boys and girls, statistically significant relationship exists between low self-esteem and experiences of bullying.

In conclusion, bullying continues to be a concern always in high schools. Hence, findings have an implication on the staff, teaching and parent community in addition to mental health professional dealing with children and adolescents, bullying prevention programs need to be incorporated in school curricula and should also include substantive instruction on bullying.

Table 3: Gender differences in Self Esteem and Bullying Behaviour of the Sample

Independent Samples Test										
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence interval	
									Lower	Upper
Self esteem	Equal variances assumed	7.684	.006	-.216	118	.829	-.167	.772	-1.695	1.362
Verbal Bullying	Equal variances assumed	9.091	.003	3.718	118	.000**	3.100	.834	1.449	4.751
Social Bullying	Equal variances assumed	10.654	.001	3.228	118	.002**	2.433	.754	.941	3.926
Physical Bullying	Equal variances assumed	6.526	.012	4.634	118	.000**	3.183	.687	1.823	4.544

Verbal Victim	Equal variances assumed	.118	.732	.471	118	.639	.550	1.168	-1.762	2.862
Social victim	Equal variances assumed	.144	.705	-.452	118	.652	-.517	1.143	-2.780	1.747
Physical victim	Equal variances assumed	16.416	.000	4.408	118	.000**	3.617	.820	1.992	5.241

** . significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Fig. 3: Self-Esteem scores comparison between genders

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